

Aquatic hyphomycete spore (conidium) isolation for culturing

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Introduction

This protocol aims to assist enthusiastic individuals and researchers alike, in their pursuit and attempt to establish fungal cultures by isolating living spores (conidia) of aquatic hyphomycetes from freshwater samples (both foam and leaf-bag trap induction). The protocol is divided into a list of materials, followed by instructions. There are supplementary protocols at the end of this document detailing the preparation of various culture media and solutions used in the main protocol. There are alternative options when available, at the end of this document.

List of materials

For field

- Cooler box (with ice blocks)
- Petri dishes with Malt Agar + antibiotics (MAA 0.1 %) ¹, sealed with parafilm
- Tools for collecting foam

For lab

- Dissecting (Stereo) microscope
- Classic microscope
- Blades
- Micro-spatulas, tiny needles, or similar tools with very small flat tips
- Bunsen burner
- Ethanol solution (EtOH 70 %)
- Fresh Petri dishes with Malt Agar (MA 1 %) ²
- England Finder Slide ³

¹ Or any classic fungal culture media with lower concentration and antibiotics.

² Or any classic fungal culture media.

³ Or any microscope slide allowing for position identification.

Steps

For field

1. Collect some foam (or a spore suspension)
2. Briefly open a MAA plate, put in a small amount of foam
3. Close the lid and seal the plate with parafilm
4. Spread the foam/water evenly on the agar surface by pivoting the plate
5. Label the plate and store in the cooler box

Important note: Ideally, process the plates under 48 hrs, for easy spore identification and isolation.

For lab

1. Clean and disinfect all tools and the working area with both microscopes next to each other
2. Create a sterile zone (including both microscopes) with a Bunsen burner, all following steps should be done inside the zone
3. Sterilise a blade with EtOH, and pass over the burner to burn and evaporate the remaining alcohol, let the blade cool
4. Open a MAA plate with spores, with the blade, cut out a piece of agar, and place it on top of the England Finder slide
5. Mount the slide under the classic microscope⁴, observe and identify the spores of interest, note down the position with the code on the slide (Be careful to not move the agar piece on the slide)
6. Note down as many spore positions as one desires from the same piece of agar
7. Move the slide to the dissecting microscope with proper lighting
8. Zoom in to a marked position, and locate the spore
9. With the help of tiny needles or micro-spatulas, carefully carve out the agar with the spore on it
10. Transfer to the centre of a fresh MA plate, seal the plate with parafilm
11. Label the plate with date, isolated location, and (putative) species name
12. Repeat step 8 to 11 to get one spore per MA plate
13. Incubate the plats in around 15°C (or room temperature)

⁴ The use of classic and dissecting microscope can be reversed, depending on the manipulator's preference.

14. The isolated cultures can be kept alive by periodically transfer a piece of the growing fringe of the old mycelium to the centre of a fresh MA plate.

Supplementary

Preparation of antibiotic stock solution

1. Antibiotics used: streptomycin sulphate (Strep.), ampicillin sodium salt (Amp.)
2. Under a laminar flow hood (or near a Bunsen burner) and use sterilised materials
3. For 10 ml of sterilised water: 1 g of Strep. and 0.6 g of Amp.
4. Mix well
5. Filter through a 0.22 µm pore sized filter with the help of a syringe
6. Aliquot to 0.75 ml, store frozen (-20 °C)

Preparation of 0.1 % MAA (Malt Agar with antibiotics)

1. For 500 ml of MAA: 0.5 g of malt extract, 10 g of agar in 500 ml of water
2. Autoclave a15 min at 120 °C
3. Let cool, add 0.75 ml of antibiotic stock solution, mixing gently
4. Pour the plates under a laminar flow hood (or near a burner) and let them solidify
5. Seal the plates with parafilm and store in fridge

Preparation of 1 % MA

1. For 500 ml of MAA: 5 g of malt extract, 10 g of agar in 500 ml of water
2. Autoclave a15 min at 120 °C
3. Pour the plates under a laminar flow hood (or near a burner) and let them solidify
4. Seal the plates with parafilm and store in fridge

Alternative options

- Electric Bunsen burner is an alternative for no open flame requirement.
- Premade culture plates are commercially available for people without lab access.